

Use Of Social Media In Electoral Process During General Elections 2018 In Punjab, Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Elections, Social media, Voters, Voting Behavior, Punjab,</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5142596</p>	<p><i>Social media is known to be a platform for sharing ideas, thoughts, awareness including the exchange of political awareness and political ideas, etc. Different social media tools such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, YouTube, Instagram and, IMO, etc. are being commonly used by the general public for social interaction in Pakistan. These social media tools are influential in political mobilization as well as transferrable amendments within the political setup of the country. The present study analyzes and, gauges the influence of usage of various social media tools and applications on molding the behaviors of electors during the General elections 2018 held in Punjab, Pakistan. The purpose and, major focus of the study is to measure and analyze the effect of social media on the political setup of the country, particularly in Punjab province. The findings of the study are supported by a survey conducted from the population having diverse demographics viz: gender, age group, educational qualification, profession, and, localities, etc. Results of the study depict that social media has been influential on the political behavior of the young population of Punjab province in the country.</i></p>

Introduction

The term social media is defined as the media which allows its users to interact with each other, share information, ideas, thoughts, etc. by using the internet, mobile phones, or other technological devices. Social media is significantly used for the purposes such as news and information sharing, various political and social campaigns, propaganda, etc. Due to easier access, the rapid use of social media has been dramatically increased, and people are switching towards social media. The increasing ratio of social media users has made social networking sites revenue generation industries. Technological advancement has introduced various platforms for social interaction among the general public where a variety of information is exchanged that has considerably impacted the decision-making, attitudes, and behaviors of a common man (Kurfi, 2015).

Different Political Parties, social activists are now extensively using social media for the promotion of their political agendas and campaigns. A very famous example of the usage of social media tools in politics by the protestors, social activists, demonstrators has been seen during the Arab Spring movements in the year 2010. The power of the use of social media has also been witnessed in the year 2014 when millions of protestors took to the streets of Missouri, Ferguson, to register their protest against the lethal police shooting of defenseless youngster American namely Michael Brown, the information and news of this brutal shooting disseminated widely through social media (Bonilla & Rosa, 2015). Various political parties and groups are effectively utilizing online social media networking sites and platforms such as for weblogs, different social networking websites to disseminate information on various political issues, policies, manifestos, etc. to the general public (Herman, 2012; Herman & Kim, 2014).

Likewise, in other countries, the rapid usage of various social media platforms in Pakistan is also increasing with every passing day. It has been actively used in Pakistan and users of social media, freely record their feedback, comments, sharing in any political, social movements in the country. Social media has become a strong tool for social and political campaigns. During elections in Pakistan, social media was used for propaganda purposes, defamation, and fundraising (Ghani, et al, 2020).

Media is used as an agenda-setting tool to build public opinion is acknowledged throughout the globe. Election campaigns to influence the voters towards a particular political party are frequently run on media. However, due to diversity in existing political cultures, the influence of media campaigns on the voting behavior of individuals remains distinctive. The present research study focuses to analyze and explain the influence of social media campaigns carried out by the mainstream political parties of Pakistan on the voting behavior of individuals during elections held in 2018. In these elections, Pakistan Muslim League (Nawaz), Pakistan People's Party,

and Pakistan Tehreek-e-Insaf were considered as main leading political parties in Punjab. Therefore, the present research study would evaluate the social media campaigns launched by these mainstream parties.

Although, these parties have also contested in general elections of Punjab in the past, wherein Pakistan Muslim League (Nawaz) and Pakistan People's Party appeared as the two largest parties in various elections held in the past. Pakistan Tehreek-e-Insaf emerged as a notable third party in the country during the general elections held in 2013 both on provincial and National Assemblies in Punjab. According to the available facts, PTI and various other mainstream parties launched special media campaigns to grab the attention of the voters of Punjab during the general elections. The present research work will focus to measure the effects of special media campaigns launched by the mainstream parties for electoral support.

General Elections (2018) in Pakistan

To elect the members of the national assembly of Pakistan and members of four provincial assemblies i.e. Punjab, Sindh, KPK, and Baluchistan, General Elections were held in the country on dated 25th July 2018 wherein main contesting parties in elections were PTI, PML-N, and PPP. PML-N and PPP have been the two largest parties in several previous elections in the country. In the 2013 elections, PTI was emerged as the third-largest political party in Pakistan whereas PTI dominant the elections campaigns in 2018 and remained successful in the elections. PML-N, PTI, and, PPP had paid special attention to launch media campaigns in elections to attract voters from all over Pakistan. According to a study, Pakistani politicians i.e. Imran Khan, Shehbaz Sharif, and Maryam Nawaz are the most active politicians on Twitter. This study was conducted two weeks before the general elections of 2018. Further, the study reveals that the most popular politician on Facebook is PTI leader Imran Khan who has 8.120 Million followers whereas PML-N leader Shahbaz Sharif has 2.08 Million followers and Maryam Nawaz has 666,003 followers and PPP leader Bilawal Bhutto Zardari have 0.11 Million followers (Rehmat & Alam, 2018).

Objectives

This research paper aims to investigate and explore the usage and significance of Social media in election campaigns in Punjab, Pakistan particularly during General Elections held in 2018. The key objectives are as under:

1. To know the importance of social media in electoral process
2. To know and evaluate the effectiveness of social media campaigns in the electoral process
3. To know and find out political awareness obtained by the voters through social media campaigns

Significance

The increasing trend of the use of social media platforms in political campaigns in Pakistan has grabbed the attention of the researcher. The usefulness of social media in general elections 2018 in Punjab province will be examined as this dimension needs to be addressed.

Statement of the problem

The researcher will investigate the usage and effectiveness of social media in election campaigns during the general election 2018 in Punjab province by various political parties. This study will also investigate on how social media platform is helpful in political mobilization and awareness of voters.

H-1

Social media campaigns in general elections have created a positive impact on the voting behavior of the general public

The rationale of Hypothesis 1

Political campaigns launched by different political parties in general elections by using various social media have created a positive impact on the voting behavior of their users. Mainstream political parties designed and launched various political campaigns on different social media tools to disseminate awareness, political awareness about the party, political manifestos, policies, and other useful information for their voters. Special

political contents are also disseminated on different social media applications to educate the voters and to change their voting trend or behavior.

H-2

Social media political campaigns disseminate hate against rival parties.

The rationale of Hypothesis 2

Most of the political campaigns on social media are designed just to defame rival parties. Contents of such political campaigns consist of the hate, abusive language only. It does not educate the voters rather it is exaggeration, and propaganda only.

Research Questions

1. Whether the political campaigns on social media disseminate political wisdom for the masses?
2. Whether the social media campaigns in general elections spread political awareness?
3. Whether political campaigns on social media have made a positive impact on the voters?
4. Whether social media political campaigns fulfill the requirements of voters with their healthy contents?

Literature Review

Fenton & Barassi (2011) contended that a tremendous increase in usage of social media asks for a reevaluation of the significance of intervened political support in the social circles. Social media is a form of mass media wherein any individual can get an innovative, creative and artistic sovereignty. Social media also support and promote political participation either by an individual or form of groups and hold the key to empowerment, and resistance.

Bratu (2013) states that social media networking sites provide a platform that brings the leadership of a party and their followers, voters closer. Social media also provides easy access to the voters to communicate with their party leadership. The researcher argues that political campaigns create an extraordinary impact on the voting behaviors of the voters to cast their vote according to their own choice.

Usman, *et al* (2013) illustrates the usage of social media tools and applications in Pakistan's political scenario is increasing day by day. Leading political leaders are commonly using social media applications such as Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, and, Twitter, etc. to encourage and, engage their supporters and voters. Renowned political parties and groups are also using social media networking sites to disseminate their political slogans, political agendas, opinion building, etc.

Wasswa, (2013) describes that a powerful, motivational online election campaign parallel to other communication media such as print, electronics, etc. can be influential upon voting behaviors of the individuals.

Prat & Strömberg (2013), describe that social media is new information technology that is based on information communication networks wherein the user of the technology formed contents, disseminates them, gets feedback on the contents, makes virtual relationships, etc. The rapid growth of the internet in the present era has dramatically changed the mode of communications. It has made the distribution of information easier, speedy, cheaper, easily accessible to everyone and therefore there is libertarian admittance to the creation and the utilization of information

Wolfsfeld, *et al.* (2013) state that two broad theoretical principles exist. According to the researcher's first principle is that any individual could not comprehend the function of social media in combined or group action without initial making into account the world of politics in which they work whereas the second principle is about the enhanced use of the new media which is liable to follow a considerable amount of demonstration & protest movement than to go before it.

According to Falck *et al.* (2014), excess use of the internet had negatively affected the voter's turnout during elections. The researchers reveal that the other mode of media has contained better information as compared to the networking sites and the overcrowded internet.

Highfield (2017), portrays that the use of terminologies, online and offline are commonly used and connected to everybody's social life including politicians. Living in the present online atmosphere is a new and normal

phenomenon. Sharing and posting of personal information either a politician or a common citizen on social media i.e. integral, Facebook, Twitter, etc. become a necessary part of one's life. The researcher argues that exploring the politician's day-to-day activities on social media becomes a normal practice. This trend shows the importance and usefulness of social media in the country.

Gil de Zúñiga et al. (2017) explain that social media is playing a leading role in today's media framework; individuals receive news information through their peers, friends, social networking sites and remained well aware and well informed. Researchers further argued that social media users who receive news information are fewer users of traditional media sources. According to the researcher, news information continues to improve social, political information and learning, if it is actively perceived.

Research Methodology

To know and measure the impact of election campaigns on individuals, voters, survey research was conducted by the researcher. The population selected for the survey was the voters of Punjab province who were the regular users of social media applications. In this context, a survey was conducted in different areas of Punjab, during the month of March-July 2018. In this regard, a questionnaire was prepared which comprises of close-ended questions to obtain feedback from the participants. The questionnaire was distributed among one thousand (1000) respondents. However, about nine hundred and ten (910) respondents have submitted their responses. Later on, the data was analyzed with the help of SPSS.

Survey Results

This section shows the outcome of the survey which illustrates a valuable approach to understand the development in present political and electoral tactics due to the progress and growth in media and technology. Results of the questions asked during the survey from the participants are elaborated hereunder.

Table-1: How regularly do you use social media?

	Very Regularly	Regularly	To some extent	Rarely	Never
Frequency	360	337	153	49	11
Percentage	39.6	37.0	16.8	5.4	1.2

According to the results, a large number of participants have been found to be the regular users of social media whereas the rest of the participants are not regular users of social media. The results reveal that the majority of the sample population selected for the present research study is common users of social media and all the participants are very well familiar with the use of social media applications.

Table-2: To what extent do election campaigns on social media have an impact on voting behaviors?

	Very much	Much	Neutral	To some extent	Not at all
Frequency	221	441	106	103	39
Percentage	24.3	48.5	11.6	11.3	4.3

The results of Table-2 depict that majority of respondents i.e. 48.5% opined that the use of social media partially affects voting behavior whereas 24.3% of respondents opined that social media greatly influenced voting behaviors. 11.3% of respondents considered that social media have influenced them to some extent. However, the rest of the participants did not share their opinion and submitted a neutral response.

Table-3: Do you believe that social media platform is helpful with election campaigns?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Frequency	207	447	146	79	31
Percentage	22.8	49.1	16.0	8.7	3.4

According to the survey results majority of participants, about 71.9% opined and acknowledged the significance of the usage of social media during election campaigns, whereas 16.04% of respondents did not share their opinion, and the use of social media in election campaigns was not acknowledged by the rest of the participants.

Table-4: Do you believe that, in comparison to other forms of electronic media, social media plays a significant role in election campaigns?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Frequency	201	393	167	111	38
Percentage	22.1	43.2	18.3	12.2	4.2

The survey results reveal that majority of participants about 65% agreed and supported the argument that social media is very important as compared with the other forms of electronic media during election campaigns as it influences the public and attracts the voters. 18.4% of participants did not share their views and remained neutral. However, about 16.4% of respondents opposed the statement.

Table-5: Do you think that the 2018 general elections were social media elections?

	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
Frequency	130	343	175	197	65
Percentage	14.3	37.7	19.2	21.6	7.2

Results of Table-5 show that more than half of respondents thought the 2018 General Elections were social media elections. However, a significant number of participants opposed the argument, and about 19.2% of respondents did not share the opinion.

Table-6: What is your level of interest in political content on social media?

	Facebook		WhatsApp		YouTube		Twitter		Instagram		Others	
	f	%	f	%	F	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Very Much	311	34.1	242	26.6	253	27.8	194	21.3	101	11.1	126	13.9
Much	258	28.4	217	23.8	207	22.7	196	21.6	76	8.4	103	11.3
To some extent	158	17.4	157	17.3	177	19.5	123	13.5	147	16.2	157	17.2
Rarely	108	11.9	116	12.7	112	12.3	134	14.7	132	14.5	150	16.5
Not at all	75	8.2	178	19.6	161	17.7	263	28.9	454	49.8	374	41.1

According to the findings, Facebook is the most widely used social media platform for election campaigns in Punjab, but other platforms such as WhatsApp, YouTube, and Twitter were also widely used for the dissemination and promotion of political content on social media stage.

Table-7: How much did the information you got from various social media groups impact your voting decision?

	Facebook		WhatsApp		YouTube		Twitter		Instagram		Others	
	F	%	f	%	F	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Very Much	389	42.7	150	16.5	167	18.3	197	21.6	95	10.4	103	11.3
Much	213	23.4	186	20.4	204	22.4	102	11.2	81	8.9	89	9.8
To some extent	102	11.2	197	21.7	186	20.4	132	14.5	179	19.7	184	20.2
Rarely	90	9.9	112	12.3	134	14.7	159	17.5	126	13.8	163	17.9
Not at all	116	12.8	265	29.1	220	24.2	320	35.2	430	47.2	371	40.8

According to the results, social media groups i.e. Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube considered as the common and influential social media tools that influenced the participants in decision making to cast their vote. A

significant number of participants opined that the political stuff, material, etc. shared on the Facebook pages played a vital role in making their voting decisions. Participants considered that social media tools viz: Twitter, Facebook, WhatsApp, YouTube, etc. played a significant role in making their voting decisions.

Table-8: How often were the factors that influenced voting behavior discussed on various social media tools during the general elections 2018?

	Ethnicity		Biradarisam		Personality		Political Party affiliation		Others	
	f	%	f	%	F	%	f	%	f	%
Very Often	212	23.3	217	23.9	288	31.7	266	29.2	242	26.6
Often	288	31.7	296	32.5	239	26.3	195	21.4	214	23.5
To some extent	190	20.9	224	24.6	206	22.6	217	23.8	193	21.2
Rarely	135	14.8	101	11.1	104	11.4	125	13.7	157	17.3
Not at all	85	9.3	72	7.9	73	8	108	11.9	104	11.4

Results of the survey illustrate that majority of participants shared their opinion and disclosed that ethnicity, Biradarisam, the personality of the candidate, party affiliation, etc. discussed on social media sites and these factors are involved and influential upon voting patterns in the Punjab general elections.

Table-9: To what extent did you share political information collected from various social media platforms with others?

	Friends / Colleagues		Family		Peer Groups		Neighbors		Others	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Very Often	336	36.9	258	28.3	202	22.2	126	13.8	130	14.3
Often	239	26.3	224	24.6	179	19.7	147	16.1	107	11.8
To some extent	147	16.1	188	20.7	213	23.4	199	21.9	211	23.2
Rarely	106	11.6	136	14.9	147	16.1	167	18.4	224	24.6
Not at all	83	9.1	105	11.5	169	18.6	271	29.8	238	26.1

According to the results of Table-9, a large number of participants opined that they commonly discuss and share the political contents and political campaigns launched on social media with others, particularly with their family members and friends. Participants also revealed that they also share the information they get from social media with various peer groups, neighbors, and other people. They also share the information they get from social media with various peer groups, neighbors, and other people.

Table-10: How much information about political campaigns did you get from social media for mainstream political parties?

	Pakistan Muslim League (N)				Pakistan People's Party				Pakistan Tehreek-e-Insaf						
	Very Much	To some extent	Rarely	Not at all	Very Much	Some what	Rarely	Not at all	Very Much	Some what	Rarely	Not at all			
Party Chairman	30.3	31.7	17	11.5	9.5	31.4	26.2	12.3	15.3	14.8	25.2	17.3	16.6	19.5	21.4

Manifesto	16.2	20.4	21.6	23. 3	18. 5	29. 2	25. 3	16	17. 7	11.8	22.1	18.7	16.7	21.4	21.1
Party Slogans	25.1	21.2	20.5	15. 8	17. 4	34	25. 6	15. 3	13. 1	12	22.8	19.3	18.4	19.3	20.2
Party Songs	22.6	23	22.9	15. 1	16. 4	17. 3	19. 8	16. 4	24. 6	21.9	21.8	14.3	16.4	20.2	27.3
Candidate	24.4	22.2	23.7	16. 6	13. 1	30. 8	27. 2	17. 4	12. 2	12.4	22.4	16.5	17.7	22.2	21.2
Others	32.1	30.3	11.5	11. 4	14. 7	16. 2	12. 5	17. 8	23. 4	30.1	16.3	12.5	22.6	23.7	24.9

The survey results depict that majority of the participants opined that they obtained a lot of information about the party's leadership on social media. Various political parties in the country publicized their political programs, manifestos to get the attention of their voters. The mainstream political parties also share their stance and party policy on different National, International and social issues during the elections. In General Elections, 2018 the main political parties had also circulated their party manifestos on various social media tools. In this regard, a significant number of participants shared that they have received information regarding their party manifestos PML-N (37%), PPP (42%), and PTI (40%). Punjabi political parties made extensive use of party songs and slogans to attract supporters and voters. Candidates often used social media to launch their election campaigns to educate and reassure their supporters. According to the survey results, PPP candidates (58%) appeared on social media to interact with their voters during election campaigns as compared with PML-N candidates (48%), and PTI candidates (36%). Overall, the findings show that mainstream political parties have confidence in and rely on social media to promote their election campaigns. The transformation and change of strategies used in election campaigns by political parties reflect the utility, strength, and importance of social media in social and political events.

Conclusion

This paper examines the role of social media in the Punjab province of Pakistan's general election campaigns in 2018. The research is based on a quantitative analysis of the results of a survey conducted in Punjab to gauge public opinion. According to the survey's results, social media has grown in popularity and importance in political campaigns over the years. The growing importance of social media in the world has had serious ramifications for the electoral fortunes of various political parties. The result depicts widespread use of social media for political and election purposes. The findings of the survey depict that various social media applications & tools viz: WhatsApp, Facebook, Twitter, and YouTube, etc. are excessively being used for the circulation of party manifestos, policy positions, political slogans, and songs. The platform of social media is also used to build and promote a positive image of the Party leadership and it is also used to defame the image of leadership of rival parties. According to the results of the survey, a majority of participants opined that they use social media tools to obtain political content and are subsequently influenced through the contents. Most of the respondents also shared that discussions in a political talk show on social media regarding the voter's choice also helpful and they also share such discussions with their family members, friends, and other social circles. It shows that social media influences both social media user's and non-users voting behavior and decision-making. It's worth noting that many participants agreed that social media is much more important and effective than other electronic media, especially when it comes to election campaigns. The General Elections 2018 were even referred to by the respondents as "social media elections." The mainstream Punjabi parties, namely the PTI, PML-N, and PPP, have recognized the value and importance of social media platforms, and have launched special election campaigns on social media in the General Elections of 2018. Furthermore, the survey's findings show that, in comparison to Pakistan Tehrek-e-Insaf, the Pakistan Muslim League (Nawaz) and Pakistan People's Party are both serious about using social media tools. In the 2018 General Elections, the PPP was unable to retain its electoral support in Punjab, and the PTI emerged as the province's second-largest party. As a result, it is argued that, while social media is a very helpful platform for contemporary politics, it does not guarantee a party's election victory. The research also shows that many factors play a role in determining a political party's electoral destiny.

Recommendations

Following are some recommendations for future studies:

- Similar type of research work can also be conducted in other provinces of Pakistan to know the. Impact of social media on electoral process there.

- Assessment of leading political parties in general elections can also be examined conducting a research study.
- A research work could be undertaken to know and evaluate social media approach towards general elections.

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